

Colibrys sensors: test different power supply sources

1. Goal

Goal of the test is to evaluate different power supply sources for the sensor and choose an appropriate one, with low noise.

2. Setup

- Colibrys on Evolution Board (with and without LPF)
- Power Supplies:
 - o Laboratory Power Supply
 - o Power Bank
 - o Battery as Power Supply: 4.73V
 - o Raspberry Pi 5V Out ADC Board
- Oscilloscope

Pin assignment Colibrys:

- Blue = GND
- Red = VCC
- Yellow = Vout (Sensor's output signal)

Pin assignment Battery:

- Black = GND
- Red = VCC

3. Data Analysis

- Files Location: SVN\spark_sling_load\trunk\09_Sensors\Colibrys\Test Power Supply
- Procedure:
 - o Measurement acquisition time: +/- 250 ms
 - o Csv File generated from oscilloscope and copied to computer
 - o Import Csv File in Matlab
 - o Plot Data

4. Outcome

Battery power supply is the most suitable for Colibrys sensors, since it has less noise than the others.